

INSIGHTS ON HYPERGLYCEMIA'S IMPACT ON THE METABOLIC PATHWAYS ASSOCIATED WITH DIABETIC RETINOPATHY: A LITERATURE REVIEW

Perspective asupra impactului hiperglicemiei asupra căilor metabolice asociate cu retinopatia diabetică: o revizuire a literaturii de specialitate

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Summary. Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a leading cause of vision impairment and blindness in diabetics. This review examines how hyperglycemia affects the metabolomic profile of retinal tissues, contributing to DR. Hyperglycemia disrupts retinal metabolism, causing the production of harmful metabolites and induction of oxidative stress. Key findings highlight alterations in glucose metabolism, increased polyol pathway flux, accumulation of sorbitol and fructose, and dysregulation of lipid metabolism. Additionally, hyperglycemia-driven changes in inflammatory pathways contribute to retinal cell damage and vascular dysfunction. The review underscores the significance of metabolomics in understanding the molecular mechanisms underlying DR and identifies potential biomarkers and therapeutic targets for early detection and intervention. Understanding these metabolic changes lays the groundwork for developing targeted therapies to slow the progression of DR and preserve vision in diabetic patients.

Key words: diabetic retinopathy, hyperglycemia, metabolomics, retinal tissue, metabolic profiling, biomarkers.

Introduction

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is one of the most known and affecting microvascular complication of diabetes mellitus (DM), characterized by progressive retinal damage, that can induce vision loss¹.

Hyperglycemia is the primary driver of DR, promoting the cascade of metabolic and biochemical alterations within retinal tissues. Metabolomics and proteomics, the compre-

¹ N. Cheung, P. Mitchell, T.Y. Wong, Diabetic retinopathy, in: LANCET, 2010, vol. 376, n.9735, pp. 124–136. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(09)62124-3

hensive analysis of small molecules, metabolites and proteins within biological samples, provides critical insights into these changes².

Even with tight glycemic and blood pressure control, some diabetic patients develop DR due to metabolic memory, where cells exposed to long-term hyperglycemia retain the adverse effects of the earlier high blood sugar environment, increasing vulnerability to complications³.

This review synthesizes current research on the impact of hyperglycemia on the proteomic/metabolomic profile of retinal tissues and elucidates its role in the pathogenesis of diabetic retinopathy.

Materials and Methods

A comprehensive search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases using the keywords “diabetic retinopathy”, “hyperglycemia”, “proteomics”, “metabolomics”, “retinal tissue” and “metabolic profiling.” Mainly, articles published from 2000 to 2024 were included to capture relevant advancements in the field. The exception was several studies used for historical data. Studies were included if they investigated the proteomic/metabolomic profile of retinal tissues in diabetic models or patients, explored the biochemical pathways affected by hyperglycemia in the context of DR, and at the same time provided insights into the role of altered metabolites in DR pathogenesis. Studies focusing solely on systemic metabolomics without specific analysis of retinal tissues or those lacking robust methodological details were excluded.

Results

It is known that the pathogenesis of DR is very intricate, encompassing various pathways, which are instigated by prolonged hyperglycemia. Also, the length of time a person has had diabetes is generally recognized as a crucial factor in the development and progression of DR. According to an 8-year prospective cohort study, variations in blood glucose levels are associated with the onset of DR⁴.

As it was mentioned, chronic hyperglycemia is the primary pathogenic factor in DR. Most meta-analyses emphasize that the duration of diabetes and the level of glycemia, as reflected by HbA1c, are the most significant risk factors for the onset and progression of the disease⁵. The study of Kapna et al. (2020) supports this statement. They demonstrated that HbA1C is a significant predictor for early depiction of DR cases. Moreover, it was shown that the prevalence and severity of DR enhanced with increasing levels of HbA1C⁶. Another study

² X.W. Hou, Y. Wang, C.W Pan, Metabolomics in Diabetic Retinopathy: A Systematic Review, in: INVEST OPHTHALMOL VIS SCI, 2021, vol. 62, n.10, pp. 4. doi:10.1167/iovs.62.10.4

³ L. Zhang, B. Chen, L. Tang, *Metabolic memory: mechanisms and implications for diabetic retinopathy*, in: DIABETES RES CLIN PRAC, 2012, vol. 96, n.3, pp. 286–293. doi: 10.1016/j.diabres.2011.12.006

⁴ Y.T Hsieh, M.C. Hsieh, Fasting Plasma Glucose Variability Is an Independent Risk Factor for Diabetic Retinopathy and Diabetic Macular Oedema in Type 2 Diabetes: An 8-Year Prospective Cohort Study, in: CLINICAL & EXPERIMENTAL OPHTHALMOLOGY, 2020, vol. 48, pp. 470-476, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ceo.13728>

⁵ B. Hemmingsen, S.S. Lund, C. Gluud, et al. Targeting intensive glycaemic control versus targeting conventional glycaemic control for type 2 diabetes mellitus., in: Cochrane Database Syst Rev, 2013, Issue 11, Art. no.: CD008143, doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD008143.pub3

⁶ J. Kapna, D. Suman, B. Poonam, M. Lakshita, K. Dinesh, Association of glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1C) level with diabetic retinopathy in type 2 diabetes patients at tertiary care hospital,

of Zhang et al. (2023), sustained the topic by demonstrating that glycated albumin (GA)/HbA1c ratio can serve as an independent predictor for the onset and progression of DR⁷.

More or less, the entire pathological process of DR involves increased oxidative stress (OS), leading to microvascular and mitochondrial dysfunction, and chronic inflammation, resulting in inflammatory infiltration and cell necrosis³.

Starting with the first studies of Kuwabara and Cogan in 1963, retina pericytes have been identified as key initiators of vascular damage in the diabetic retina. It is known that pericytes play a crucial role in regulating blood flow, vessel permeability, and tissue perfusion, thus maintaining vascular function. This delicate balance is disrupted by hyperglycemia, which initiates events that severely impair pericyte function⁸.

The developing retina relies heavily on pericytes, and their loss is a hallmark of early DR. Factors involved in pericyte recruitment include angiopoietin-1 with its receptor Tie-2, VEGF-A with its receptor flk-1, and the PDGF-B/PDGF- β system. The exact mechanisms by which DM induces apoptosis in the retinal microvasculature remain unclear, although OS, advanced glycation end products (AGEs), upregulation of protein kinase C, increased polyol pathway flux, and focal leukostasis are likely significant contributors⁹.

Inflammation, driven by persistent hyperglycemia, induces phenotypic changes in pericytes, compromising their ability to regulate vascular tone and permeability. Meanwhile, AGEs further disrupt the communication between pericytes and endothelial cells, inducing systemic vascular dysfunction OS, that results in the overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) undermines pericyte support for vascular balance. In conclusion, OS, inflammation, and AGEs collectively impair pericyte function, disrupting vascular stability and contributing to the progression of diabetic complications¹⁰.

However, the reasons why pericytes are particularly susceptible to hyperglycemic injury, compared to other cell types in the neurovascular unit, remain unclear.

Alongside advancements in diagnostics and therapeutics, the role of glycemia and reactive metabolites in causing cellular stress and biochemical abnormalities are continuously re-evaluated, inclusively as treatment targets⁸.

The ‘unifying hypothesis’ proposed by Giacco et al. (2010) suggests that hyperglycemia damages the retina by overactivating several biochemical pathways in diabetes, all stemming from one common issue mentioned earlier: mitochondrial overproduction of ROS due to excess intracellular glucose flux¹¹. This hypothesis proposes that the forma-

in: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF OPHTHALMOLOGY SCIENCES, 2020, vol. 2(1), pp. 9-12. <https://doi.org/10.33545/26648520.2020.v2.i1a.10>

⁷ T. Zhang, X. Zheng, Association of GA/HbA1c Ratio with Diabetic Retinopathy, in: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CLINICAL MEDICINE, vol. 14, pp. 357-365. doi: 10.4236/ijcm.2023.148031

⁸ H.P. Hammes, Diabetic retinopathy: hyperglycaemia, oxidative stress and beyond, in: DIABETOLOGIA, 2018, vol.61, pp. 29-38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-017-4435-8>

⁹ S. Ejaz, I. Chekarova, A. Ejaz, A. Sohail, C.W. Lim, Importance of pericytes and mechanisms of pericyte loss during diabetes retinopathy, in: DIABETES OBES METAB, 2008, vol. 10, n.1, pp. 53-63. doi: 10.1111/j.1463-1326.2007.00795.x

¹⁰ R. Chilton, E.I. Iranpour, Z. Bloomgarden. Deciphering the connection: Diabetes, pericyte dysfunction, and their impact on cardiovascular health. in: J DIABETES, 2024, vol. 16, n.2, e13539. doi:10.1111/1753-0407.13539

¹¹ F. Giacco, M. Brownlee, Oxidative stress and diabetic complications. in: CIRC RES, 2012, vol. 107, pp. 1058–1070. doi:10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.110.223545

tion of AGEs accounts for the hyperglycemic memory of tissue damage, whereby vascular damage developed during periods of poor glycemic control persists even during cycles of euglycemia. Conversely, findings from the DCCT/EDIC study indicate that there is also a delay in worsening when transitioning to less stringent control after periods of stringent control. Therefore, persistent damage through AGEs involves permanent modifications of matrix macromolecules, intracellular components like proteins and DNA, altered protein transcription, and changed cellular functions through receptor-mediated mechanisms. Excess AGE formation and overactivation of the hexosamine pathway induce angiopoietin-2 transcription by inhibiting a transcriptional co-repressor complex from binding and silencing the angiopoietin-2 promoter.

In conclusion, the unifying hypothesis also highlights the crucial role of ROS and AGEs in sustaining vascular damage in diabetes, emphasizing the need for stringent glycemic control to prevent long-term complications¹¹.

Numerous studies are still reporting significant changes in the metabolomic profiles of retinal tissues under hyperglycemic conditions, that encompass various metabolic pathways, including glycolysis, polyol pathway, etc. This further leads to multiple alterations including the thickening of the basement membrane of retinal capillaries, increased permeability of retinal vasculature, tissue ischemia, and the generation of various vasoactive agents⁸.

Glycolysis, the most conserved metabolic pathway in biology, is tightly regulated to maintain steady-state concentrations of glycolytic intermediates. This regulation, known as regulated glycolysis, ensures metabolic balance. However, an abnormal enhancement in glycolytic flux can produce excessive intermediate metabolites, which are diverted into harmful pathways such as the polyol pathway, hexosamine pathway, diacylglycerol-dependent protein kinase C pathway, and the formation of Amadori/AGEs¹².

Moreover, the disruption between glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation causes other biochemical and molecular changes, seen in DR. These changes include miscommunication between the endoplasmic reticulum and mitochondria, and dysregulation of mitophagy. Understanding these mechanisms highlights the importance of maintaining metabolic balance to prevent and manage DR. Effective targeting of these pathways could lead to novel therapeutic interventions¹².

Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), a glycolytic enzyme, significantly impacts metabolic OS, and it is considered to play a critical role in the pathophysiology of DR, as the overproduction of ROS can damage tissues surrounding retinal blood vessels¹³. The release of LDH is minimal under normal conditions but increases substantially with enhanced cell membrane permeability, correlating with the number of damaged cells. Research indicates that unstable hyperglycemia can activate protein kinase C and trigger an OS response, while elevated glucose levels and hypoxia increase LDH levels in retinal cells¹⁴.

¹² T. Yumnamcha, M. Guerra, L.P. Singh, A.S Ibrahim. Metabolic Dysregulation and Neurovascular Dysfunction in Diabetic Retinopathy, in: ANTIOXIDANTS (BASEL), 2020, vol. 9, n. 12, pp. 1244. doi:10.3390/antiox9121244

¹³ Q. Kang, C. Yang, Oxidative stress and diabetic retinopathy: molecular mechanisms, pathogenetic role and therapeutic implications, in: REDOX BIOL, 2020, vol. 37, pp. 101799. doi: 10.1016/j.redox.2020.101799

¹⁴ J.P. De La Cruz, JA. González-Correa, A. Guerrero, F.S. de la Cuesta, Pharmacological approach to diabetic retinopathy, in: DIABETES METAB RES REV, 2004, vol. 20, nr. 2, pp. 91-113. doi: 10.1002/dmrr.432

In time, several animal studies have demonstrated the contribution of OS to the progression of DR. Some researchers suggest that LDH can serve as a biochemical marker of OS to predict the onset of DR. Additionally, studies by Yu-Shan Hsieh et al. (2022) have shown that elevated LDH levels are associated with increased glycated albumin and insulin antibody levels, further linking LDH to the pathophysiology of DR¹⁵. The study of Yang P. et al. (2024) showed that an enhanced level of LDH positively correlated with an elevated incidence of DR¹⁶. But these studies are still inconclusive, few and controversial.

While reviewing potential studies to support our purpose, we found a notable article from 1995 by M.K. Van den Enden¹⁷. The study proved that elevated glucose levels have significant effects on retinal glycolysis and sorbitol pathway metabolism. When retinas from normal male Sprague-Dawley rats were incubated with increasing concentrations of glucose, several metabolic changes were observed: – increased levels of sorbitol and triose phosphates: indicative of enhanced activity in the sorbitol pathway and glycolysis; – diminished sn-glycerol-3-phosphate levels: suggesting alterations in glycerolipid metabolism; – enhanced production of lactate and fructose: reflecting a shift towards anaerobic glycolysis and enhanced sorbitol pathway flux and finally an increased retinal lactate-pyruvate ratio: indicative of a hypoxia-like redox imbalance, or “pseudohypoxia,” caused by an increased cytosolic NADH/NAD⁺ ratio. Potentially triggering was the use of an aldose reductase inhibitor (AL 4114) that further normalized the levels of sorbitol, fructose, triose phosphates, and the lactate-pyruvate ratio, without affecting lactate production or sn-glycerol-3-phosphate levels. These findings suggest that increased retinal glucose levels caused a redox imbalance similar to hypoxia, primarily due to boosted oxidation of sorbitol to fructose. This imbalance further impaired the regulation of retinal blood flow, even in the absence of vascular structural changes, and preceded and contributed to the development of hypoxic and ischemic retinopathy in diabetes¹⁷.

Looking further, were found studies exploring the polyol pathway, a critical component of glucose metabolism, that becomes highly active in DM, disrupting the NADH/NAD⁺ balance and causing oxidative damage to DNA and proteins, which contributes to DR¹⁸.

Retinal endothelial cells participate in aldose reductase activity by expressing the aldose reductase enzyme. This enzyme catalyzes the reduction of glucose to sorbitol, the first step in the polyol pathway. Certain promoter region polymorphisms in the aldose reductase gene are linked to susceptibility and progression of DR¹⁹.

¹⁵ Y.S. Hsieh, M.C. Yeh, Y.Y. Lin, et al, Is the level of serum lactate dehydrogenase a potential biomarker for glucose monitoring with type 2 diabetes mellitus? in: FRONT ENDOCRINOL., 2022, vol. 13, pp. 1099805. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2022.1099805

¹⁶ P. Yang, W. Xu, L. Liu, G. Yang, Association of lactate dehydrogenase and diabetic retinopathy in US adults with diabetes mellitus, in: J DIABETES, 2024, vol. 16, n.1, pp. e13476. doi:10.1111/1753-0407.13476

¹⁷ MK Van den Enden, J.R. Nyengaard, E. Ostrow, J.H. Burgan, J.R. Williamson, Elevated glucose levels increase retinal glycolysis and sorbitol pathway metabolism. Implications for diabetic retinopathy. in: INVEST OPHTHALMOL VIS SCI, 1995, vol. 36, n. 8, pp. 1675-85. PMID: 7601647

¹⁸ M. Zhang, M. Zhou, X. Cai, et al. VEGF promotes diabetic retinopathy by upregulating the PKC/ET/NF-κB/ICAM-1 signaling pathway. in: EUR J HISTOCHEM, 2022, vol. 66, n. 4, pp. 3522. doi:10.4081/ejh.2022.3522

¹⁹ S.S. Garg, J. Gupta. Polyol pathway and redox balance in diabetes. in: PHARMACOL RES, 2022, vol. 182, pp. 106326. doi: 10.1016/j.phrs.2022.106326

Overexpression of aldose reductase is suggested to be a molecular mechanism in human DR by regulating the polyol (sorbitol) pathway for glucose metabolism²⁰. Specific polymorphisms in polyol pathway genes were found, with ALR2 rs759853 and SDH rs2055858 being associated with varying levels of DR risk²¹. The polyol pathway's contribution to DR pathogenesis involves modulation of OS, inflammatory responses, and homeostasis²².

The hexosamine pathway is crucial for protein maturation and cellular communication, mediating glucose metabolism and stress responses²³. This pathway contributes to metabolic diseases, including DM, and DR²⁴. The progression of DR involves excessive ROS release, inflammatory stress, and cell death^{3,25}.

These findings highlight the complex interplay between metabolic pathways and their role in the pathogenesis of diabetic complications, emphasizing the importance of targeting these pathways for therapeutic interventions.

Conclusion

The proteomic/metabolomic profiling of retinal tissues under hyperglycemic conditions reveals extensive metabolic reprogramming that underpins the pathogenesis of diabetic retinopathy. Key metabolic pathways, including glycolysis, polyol pathway, etc. are significantly disrupted, contributing to oxidative stress, inflammation, and retinal cell dysfunction.

These findings provide a comprehensive biochemical framework for understanding DR and highlight potential biomarkers and therapeutic targets. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies to track metabolic changes over the course of DR progression and evaluate the efficacy of interventions aimed at restoring metabolic homeostasis.

²⁰ N. Niimi, H. Yako, S. Takaku, et al. Aldose reductase and the polyol pathway in Schwann cells: Old and new problems. in: INT J MOL SCI, 2021, vol. 22, n. 3, pp. 1031. doi: 10.3390/ijms22031031

²¹ W. Li, S. Chen, Z. Mei, et al, Polymorphisms in sorbitol-aldose reductase (polyol) pathway genes and their influence on risk of diabetic retinopathy among Han Chinese. in: MED SCI MONIT, 2019, vol. 25, pp. 7073-78. doi:10.12659/MSM.917011

²² I.G. Obrosova, P.F. Kador. Aldose reductase/polyol inhibitors for diabetic retinopathy. in: CURR PHARM BIOTECHNOL, 2011, vol. 12, n.3, pp. 373-85. doi: 10.2174/138920111794480642

²³ M.S. Denzel, A. Antebi, Hexosamine pathway and (ER) protein quality control. in: CURR OPIN CELL BIOL, 2015, vol. 33, pp. 14-18. doi: 10.1016/j.ceb.2014.10.001

²⁴ M.Y. Wu, G.T. Yiang, T.T. Lai, C.J. Li, The oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction during the pathogenesis of diabetic retinopathy, in: OXID MED CELL LONGEV, 2018, vol. 2018, pp. 3420187. doi: 10.1155/2018/3420187

²⁵ R.A. Kowluru, A. Kowluru, M. Mishra, B. Kumar. Oxidative stress and epigenetic modifications in the pathogenesis of diabetic retinopathy, in: PROG RETINEYE RES, 2015, vol. 48, pp. 40-61. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbdis.2015.08.001